

PARAMETERS OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR FORMING A CULTURE OF INTERNATIONAL COMMUNICATION IN STUDENTS BASED ON A CULTURAL STUDIES APPROACH

Atamuradov Dilshod

Doctoral student of Urgench state university

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Abstract. *This article discusses the approaches used in preparing future teachers for the formation of the culture of inter-ethnic communication in students, the provided knowledge, their didactic description, the parameters for the formation of the necessary knowledge in this direction in future teachers. This article is important for the scientific pedagogical community, students, doctoral students and independent researchers, teachers. serves as a resource.*

Keywords: *universal human values, national values, globalization, universal culture, cultural studies approach, axiological approach, inter-ethnic harmony, tolerance, historical-cultural approaches, students, students, cultural concepts.*

Forming a culture of inter-ethnic communication among students in pedagogical processes carried out in general secondary schools should become one of the most important tasks of pedagogues. For this purpose, future teachers need to master the social experience of the people and acquire professional skills in the process of mastering educational courses such as “Education”, “Methodology of Educational Work”, “History of Pedagogy”, “History of the Uzbek Language”. In preparing students for pedagogical activities based on the approach of cultural studies, the knowledge of fake culture should be replaced by knowledge aimed at developing inter-ethnic communication skills. It should be emphasized that by presenting universal human values to students, it is possible to form goodwill, negativity and feelings towards different nationalities in them.

Today, when inter-ethnic relations have reached a new level of quality in Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to instilling universal human values into the content of education. The task of educating specialists with a broad cultural outlook requires their intellectual, spiritual, and cultural development. Adherence to the principles of mutual respect, generosity, humanity in inter-ethnic relations is considered as a valuable act. The rules defining the behavior of representatives of different nationalities, spiritual and moral qualities appear as values defining their identity. The values that exist in any society and are required to be followed are considered as national and universal values.

National values are a component of national spirituality, which includes "spiritual heritage of nations, traditions, customs, national literature, art." "They are based on the cultural features and aspects of each nation, people or people that are passed down from generation to generation in the process of historical development. A nation is not only people who live in a certain area and speak the same language, but also a historical-social unity existing on the basis of common cultural-spiritual aspects and characteristics. Culture has been an integral part of human history since the beginning of time, it is as old as man himself. The culture of each nation is unique and unique, and it develops and improves.

Universal values "is a concept that expresses a system of values of universal importance, which is considered as a common value criterion for all people, nations and states in the world. Universal values are a very broad and diverse concept. Universal values form a system common to all people living in a certain period of social development, and are manifested in a continuous connection with other principles, in a necessary connection².

Universal values are common criteria for all peoples and nations. The main reasons for this can be explained by the following: the fact that the earth is a single living space for all people, regardless of race, nationality, religious belief, the need for spiritual and cultural development of people in the whole world, regardless of their social diversity, the increase in the number of weapons of mass destruction, the social and spiritual crisis. increased, the gene pool of humanity is endangered, the preservation of its purity is more urgent than ever, the existence of a strong need to preserve the achievements of human civilization in different eras, the need to apply the most valuable knowledge, moral concepts and models necessary for the formation of the culture of inter-ethnic communication in young people to the educational process causing Because universal human values constitute the only system that serves to form the culture of inter-ethnic communication in students.

These values are the main means of forming the skills of establishing relations with representatives of different nationalities on the basis of mutual solidarity, equality and tolerance. Human values are valuable for representatives of all nations and form the basis of people's life, lifestyle and culture.

Paying special attention to the preparation of students for the formation of the culture of inter-ethnic communication in the educational process by means of universal and national values requires the systematic presentation of knowledge in this direction. For this purpose, it is necessary to provide future teachers with knowledge about spiritual qualities such as selflessness, patriotism, patriotism, enthusiasm for the development of the country, having a civic position, realizing that Uzbekistan is the only Motherland for representatives of all nationalities, openness to all nationalities and religions, and tolerant attitude. should be considered. Because in order to effectively form the culture of inter-ethnic communication among students, first of all, the teacher himself needs to have knowledge about universal, national values, the development trends of these concepts, and their place in the national spirituality. Only on the basis of instilling these values in students, the process of effective formation of their skills related to the culture of inter-ethnic communication will accelerate.

Ensuring interethnic harmony and stability in the Republic of Uzbekistan is implemented through the development of the cultural environment. In our republic, the development of cultures and values characteristic of all nations is treated with equal respect. In this process, the main place is occupied by cultural communication between students and youth of different nationalities. Social cooperation with representatives of other nationalities, assimilation of their knowledge and experiences, to be aware of the achievements of different countries and peoples, it is of particular importance to consider expanding opportunities for cultural communication among students. Students are required to understand the content of the law in order to master the rules of mutual social cooperation. A clear manifestation of social cooperation and tolerance between representatives of different nationalities directly depends on the current level of cultural outlook of the members of the society.

Interethnic dialogue in Uzbekistan has its specific goals and objectives. First of all, it serves to establish inter-ethnic harmony in the society. In order to ensure that the languages, customs and traditions of more than 130 nationalities and peoples living in Uzbekistan are regularly respected, it is first necessary to form a clear scientific vision of interethnic communication in future teachers. In the framework of inter-ethnic relations, it is important to recognize the rights of representatives of all nationalities, to recognize all manifestations of ethnic identity. It is necessary to develop in future teachers the ability to recognize universal human values by providing knowledge about being intolerant to any forms of nationalism.

Future teachers should be given accurate information about more than 130 nationalities and peoples living in Uzbekistan, their culture and traditions. The role of national-cultural centers in ensuring international peace, stability and harmony in Uzbekistan is incomparable, and it is necessary to provide necessary information about them to future teachers.

There is a need for future teachers to familiarize themselves with the axiological directions of inter-ethnic communication. Among such directions, the following can be included: recognition of the independence of each nation, recognition of the right of each nation to be proud of its spiritual culture, recognition of the right of each nation to its own identity and freedom of conscience, recognition of the need for each nation to fight for its future, to the Motherland such as knowing that love and glorifying one's homeland is the noble goal of every nation, respecting the qualities of patriotism and patriotism of every nation's representative. These values are manifested in each nation in its own way. This, in turn, requires relying on certain pedagogical approaches in forming the culture of interethnic communication in students. In preparing future teachers for the formation of the culture of interethnic communication in students, it is of particular importance to form moral choices in them through the use of universal values. Among such values, it is possible to include the awareness of national identity, purposeful use of universal values, manifestation of one's point of view and independent choice in a multinational society. Future teachers will also be aware of the knowledge about expanding the opportunity to express the individual's identity in the process of mastering universal values.

The analysis of the sources and our observations show that enriching their cultural knowledge is of particular pedagogical importance in order to form a culture of interethnic communication among students. This direction and in order to present the acquired knowledge to the students, it is desirable that the teachers themselves have thoroughly mastered the approaches and methods of the culture of international communication. Accordingly, it is necessary to form a clear pedagogical point of view on values in future teachers. Because the valuable orientations formed in students serve as a source of guidance for their views, actions and behavior in a multinational society.

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